

MALARIA INFECTION, NUTRITION EDUCATION AND PREVENTION STRATEGIES OF PATIENTS DIAGNOSED OF MALARIA IN NIGER DELTA TEACHING HOSPITAL, OKOLOBIRI, BAYELSA STATE

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17713456>

Key words:
Malaria,
Disease,
Infection,
Nutritional
Management
and
Prevention
Strategies.

Abstract: Malaria infection is a complex disease involving the Plasmodium parasite and human host. Malaria infection remains a significant public health concern in Nigeria, particularly in the Niger Delta region. This study focuses on malaria infection, nutritional management, and prevention strategies of patients diagnosed with malaria in Niger Delta Teaching Hospital, Okolobiri, Bayelsa State. The research highlights the importance of adequate nutrition in managing malaria, as it helps strengthen the immune system, repair tissues, and prevent complications like anaemia. The study also emphasizes the role of prevention strategies, such as using insecticide-treated bed nets, eliminating mosquito breeding sites, and promoting awareness about malaria prevention. A cross-sectional design was employed, selecting 25 children aged 0-5 years with malaria disease. The result

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showed significant positive correlation between malaria infections and nutritional management ($r = 0.421$, $p < 0.05$); as well as a significant positive correlation between malaria infection and prevention strategies ($r = 0.512$, $p < 0.05$). Thus, indicating adequate nutritional management is associated with reduced severity of malaria infection, and effective prevention strategies are associated with reduced risk of malaria infection. The study concludes that healthcare providers should prioritize patient education and counselling on malaria prevention and treatment, emphasizing the importance of nutrition and prevention strategies in reducing the burden of malaria infection.

Introduction

Malaria is a protozoal disease that is transmitted by infected female Anopheles mosquitoes, this can be diagnosed through blood tests and is managed with antimalarial medications and supportive nutritional care. A female Anopheles mosquito injects its Plasmodium sporozoites into the human host's skin into the bloodstream while feeding. The sporozoites then travel to the liver and invade the liver cells (hepatocytes), where they multiply for a week or more. The parasites rupture the liver cells and release merozoites into the bloodstream. These merozoites invade red blood cells (RBCs), multiply further, causing breakdown of the red blood cells, releasing more parasites into the blood. This cyclical destruction of RBCs leads to the characteristic symptoms of malaria, such as recurrent fevers, chills, and anemia, (Foster & Walker, 2019). Gametocyte Formation: Some parasites develop into sexual forms (gametocytes), which can be ingested by another biting mosquito, continuing the

transmission cycle. Prompt and accurate diagnosis is crucial for effective management. Malaria is an endemic vector-borne parasitic disease caused by protozoan parasites of the genus Plasmodium in tropical and subtropical regions worldwide. It is an acute febrile illness caused by Plasmodium parasites, which are spread to people through the bites of infected female Anopheles mosquitoes; also it is preventable and curable (Bennink, Kiesow, Pradel, 2016).

The natural history of malaria involves the cyclic infection of humans and female Anopheles mosquitoes. In humans, the parasites grow and multiply first in the liver cells and then in the red cells of the blood, the parasites grow inside the red cells and destroy them, releasing smaller parasites (“merozoites”) that continue the cycle and invading other red cells. The blood stage parasites are those that cause the symptoms of malaria. When certain forms of blood stage parasites are ingested during blood feeding by a female anopheles mosquito, they mate in the gut

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of the mosquito and begin a cycle of growth and multiplication in the mosquito. After 10-18 days, a form of the parasite called a sporozoite migrates to the mosquito's salivary glands. When the Anopheles mosquito takes a blood meal on human, anticoagulant saliva is injected together with the sporozoites, which migrate to the liver, thereby beginning a new cycle, Center for Disease Control and Prevention (2024). At this point, the infected mosquito carries the disease from one human to another (acting as a "vector"), while infected humans transmit the parasite to the mosquito, in the human host, the mosquito vector does not suffer from the presence of the parasites.

The malaria parasite life cycle involves

a. The malaria-infected female Anopheles mosquito injects sporozoites into the human host, the sporozoites infect the liver cells and mature into schizonts, which rupture and release merozoites.

b. After this initial replication in the liver (exo-erythrocytic schizogony), the parasites undergo asexual multiplication in the erythrocytes (erythrocytic schizogony) and merozoites infect the red blood cells.

c. The ring stage trophozoites mature into schizonts, rupture to release merozoites, some parasites differentiate into sexual erythrocytic stages (gametocytes), Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2024).

d. In the blood stage the parasites are responsible for the clinical manifestations of the disease, known as the sporogonic cycle, while in the mosquito's stomach, the microgametes penetrate the macrogametes generating zygotes.

e. The zygotes in turn become motile and elongated (ookinetes), which invade the midgut wall of the mosquito where they develop into oocytes. The oocytes grow, rupture, and release sporozoites, which make their way to the mosquito's salivary glands.

f. Inoculation of the sporozoites into a new human host perpetuates the malaria life cycle, Bennink et,al. (2016).

Malaria is a life-threatening disease primarily found in tropical countries, however, without prompt diagnosis and effective treatment, a case of uncomplicated malaria can progress to a severe form of the disease, which is often fatal without treatment. Malaria is not contagious and cannot spread from one person to another. Five species of parasites can cause malaria in humans and 2 of these species – plasmodium falciparum and Plasmodium vivax – pose the greatest threat, (Singh & Daneshvar, 2013), these include – P. falciparum, P. vivax, P. ovale, P. malariae, and P. knowlesi.

There are over 400 different species of Anopheles mosquitoes and around 40, known as vector species, can transmit the disease, Whitfield, (2021). The risk of infection is higher in some areas than others depending on multiple

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Advance Journal of Nursing and Clinical Practice

Adv. J. Nur. Pract.

Vol. 8; Issue 06;

November-December 2025

ISSN: 2573 –1134

Impact Factor: 6.04

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<http://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/ajncp/index>

factors, including – the type of local mosquitoes, and the season, the risk being highest during the rainy season in tropical countries. The disease is easy enough to treat, but access to the most effective treatments remains inadequate. Over 95 per cent of all malaria deaths occur on the African continent, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, (2021).

Adequate nutrition is an important supportive measure during malaria treatment, persistent of the malaria disease can lead to tissue loss and malnutrition. Adequate hydration is important due to fever, sweating, potential diarrhea, adequate fluid intake is also recommended to prevent dehydration and help eliminate toxins. Fluids can include water, oral rehydration salts (ORS) solutions, fresh fruit juices and beverages. There should be improved calorie and protein intake, a diet rich in high-quality protein (meats, fish, eggs, legumes, milk products) is necessary for tissue repair and immune function, (Malaria treatment using diet, ghdonline.org 2016). Varied intake of fruits and vegetables helps replenish lost vitamins, like Vitamin A and C, minerals like zinc and iron should be guided by a doctor to also manage other malaria-associated symptoms. Small, frequent and easily digestible, high-carbohydrate foods are recommended to manage reduced appetite and potential digestive issues. Limit consumption of high-fat, fried and heavily processed foods, these may worsen digestive problems. Alcohol and excessive

caffeine should also be avoided as these can interfere with medication and hydration levels, (Malaria Prevention and Nutrition, gbchealth.org 2017).

Malaria remains one of the world's leading causes of morbidity and mortality with an estimated 600 000 deaths and 200 million cases annually (World Health Organization, 2014). There are several Plasmodium that cause malaria in humans, with Plasmodium falciparum accounting for the majority of severe malaria and deaths, particularly in Africa. Plasmodium vivax is a second important cause of malaria with most of the burden occurring in Asia, (Price, Tjitra and Guerra, 2007). Concurrent infection with more than one Plasmodium species is uncommon but can occur, (Sutherland, Tanomsing & Nolder, 2010). Transmission begins when a female Anopheles mosquito feeds on a person with malaria and ingests blood containing gametocytes. Objective of the study is to analyse the Malaria Infection, Nutritional Management and Prevention Strategies of patients diagnosed of Malaria in Niger Delta Teaching Hospital, Okolobiri, Bayelsa State

Literature Review

Diagnosis of malaria depends on the presence of parasites in the blood, usually by microscopy. Additional laboratory findings may include mild anemia, mild decrease in blood platelets (thrombocytopenia), elevation of bilirubin and

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elevation of amino transferases. Malaria can be diagnosed by finding parasites on microscopic examination of thick or thin blood smears. The infecting species (which determines therapy and prognosis) is identified by characteristic features on smears. If the initial blood smear is negative, additional smears should be repeated at 12- to 24-hour intervals until 3 smears are negative.

Thin blood smears stained with Wright-Giemsa stain allow assessment of parasite morphology within red blood cells (RBCs), often speciation, and determination of percentage parasitemia (parasite density), evaluated using oil immersion magnification of portions of the smear where RBCs are more or less touching, which should show about 400 RBCs per field. Thick smears are more sensitive but more difficult to prepare and interpret as the RBCs are broken down before staining. Sensitivity and accuracy of the results depend on the examiner's experience (Picot, et.al. 2020).

Diagnosis include - Light microscopy of blood (Field Stain); Rapid diagnostic tests that detect Plasmodium antigens or enzymes in blood; Polymerase Chain Reaction; Fever and chills in an immigrant or travellers returning from an endemic region should prompt immediate investigation for malaria.

Mode of transmission

- a. Transmitted by various species of infective female Anopheles mosquitoes. Most species feed in the night, some important vectors have biting peaks at dusk or in the early morning (Heymann, 2004).
- b. Injection or transfusion of contaminated blood may also transmit malaria, (though very rare).
- c. Congenital transmission is rare.
- d. The mosquitoes that can transmit malaria are found not only in malaria endemic areas, but are also found in areas where malaria has been eliminated. The latter areas are thus constantly at risk of re-introduction of the disease.

	Pre-patent period (Time between infective bite and detection of the parasites in a blood smear)	Incubation period (Time between infective bite and the onset of clinical symptoms)
P. falciparum	6-12 days	9-14 days
P. vivax	8-12 days	12-18 days
P. ovale	8-12 days	12-18 days
P. malariae	12-16 days	18-40 days

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Adv. J. Nur. Pract.

Vol. 8; Issue 06;

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ISSN: 2573 –1134

Impact Factor: 6.04

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

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However, some strains of *Plasmodium vivax* in the temperate climates may not cause clinical illness for months to > 1 year after infection. Some strains of *Plasmodium vivax*, may have an incubation period of 8-10 months or longer (Heymann, 2004). Transfusion associated malaria (rare) has a shorter incubation period (Bradley & Bannister, 2003). Malaria in humans is caused by four different species of the protozoan parasite *Plasmodium*: *Plasmodium falciparum*, *Plasmodium vivax*, *Plasmodium ovale* and *Plasmodium malariae*.

Malaria produces a string of recurrent attacks, each of which has 3 stages - chills, followed by fever and then sweating.

i. *Plasmodium Falciparum* is responsible for most malaria deaths worldwide, it may present with a varied clinical picture, including one or more of the following, fever, chills, sweats, anorexia, nausea, headache, muscle and joint pain, cough and diarrhoea. If treated inadequately the disease may progress to severe malaria, of which the most important manifestations are; acute encephalopathy (cerebral malaria), severe anemia, renal failure, hypoglycaemia and respiratory distress, (Sutherland et.al. 2010).

ii. *Plasmodium vivax*, is the most geographically widespread of the species, it produces less severe symptoms including, a slowly rising fever of several days duration followed by a shaking chill and rapidly rising

temperature, commonly accompanied by headache, nausea and profuse sweating. Following a fever free period this cycle of symptoms may reoccur daily, every other day or every third day. An untreated primary attack may last from a week to a month. Relapses can occur at irregular intervals, (Sutherland et.al. 2010).

iii. *Plasmodium malariae*, infections produces typical malaria symptoms and can persist in the blood for very long periods (possibly for life) without producing symptoms.

iv. *Plasmodium ovale*, is less common and can cause relapses.

Pregnant women are particularly vulnerable to malaria as pregnancy reduces a woman's immunity to malaria, making her more susceptible to malaria infection and increasing the risk of illness, severe anaemia and death. For the unborn child, maternal malaria increases the risk of spontaneous abortion, stillbirth, premature delivery and low birth weight - a leading cause of child mortality. Persons who are partially immune or who have been taking prophylactic drugs may show an atypical clinical picture and a prolonged incubation period.

Nutritionally managing a malaria patient is critical because malaria infection induces metabolic stress and nutrient imbalances that can worsen disease severity, to hinder or delay recovery. Proper nutrition helps to strengthen the immune system, repair tissues,

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prevent complications like anemia and support overall recovery. Nutritional management of the malaria patient involves supporting the increased calorie & protein needs from fever and illness while staying hydrated. Nutrition should be focused on easy-to-digest, nutrient-rich foods like lean proteins, whole grains, fruits and vegetables high in vitamins A and C, while avoiding fats, fried, spicy and highly processed foods, and adequate fluid intake is important to the patient daily.

Reasons for nutritional management include:

- i. To support the immune function: Adequate Nutrition is essential for fighting infection. Deficiencies in micronutrients like vitamins A, C and E, and minerals like zinc, iron, and selenium, supports the immune system and make the body more resistance to severe malaria and secondary infections.
- ii. Prevent and manage anemia: The malaria parasite infect and destroys the red blood cells, which can lead to severe anemia. A diet that is rich in iron, folic acid, and vitamin B12, along with appropriate supplementation (as directed by a healthcare provider), will help in the production of healthy red blood cells to manage anemia.
- iii. Adequate nutrition supports in tissue repairs and growth: Malaria causes massive tissue loss and muscle breakdown. A high-protein diet is crucial for protein synthesis,

tissue building and prevention of muscle loss, especially in growing children.

- iv. Maintain Hydration and Electrolyte Balance: Fever, sweating, vomiting and diarrhea are all signs of malaria, which can lead to significant fluid and electrolyte loss. Generous fluid intake (3 to 3.5 liters daily) of water, oral rehydration solutions and variety of fresh fruit juices are vital to prevent dehydration and help flush out toxins from the system.
- v. Reduce Complications: Adequate nutrition helps to prevent nutritional deficiencies, while nutritional deficiencies caused by malaria diseases can contribute to a range of adverse outcomes, like impaired growth and development in children and a high mortality risks.
- vi. Adequate nutrition will improve drug efficacy: Proper nutritional status can enhance the effectiveness of antimalarial drugs to improve the patient's response to treatment.
- vii. Adequate nutritional management will address the complex interplay between infection and the body's metabolic response, alongside antimalarial medication to ensure a fast recovery.

Nutrition for Malaria Patients should include:

- a) High-calorie and carbohydrate: Grains eg rice, oatmeal and whole-grain bread provide energy. Starchy vegetables like sweet potatoes and other are also good choices.

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b) Protein: Are essential for tissue repair, eg lean meats (chicken, turkey), fish, eggs, lentils and beans.

c) Variety of Fruits and vegetables: They are rich in vitamins and antioxidants, eg, oranges, berries, spinach, carrots and pawpaw.

d) Healthy unsaturated vegetable oils: Eg, avocados, nuts, seeds and olive oil can support immune function.

Prevention and control

Awareness	Know about the risk of malaria infection
Bites	Prevent or avoid
Compliance	With appropriate malaria chemoprophylaxis
Diagnose	Breakthrough malaria swiftly and obtain treatment promptly

Strategies of malaria prevention – mosquitoes breed in water and they are especially more during the rainy season and the most effective prevention is to:

a. Avoid bites by sleeping under insecticide-treated bed nets.

b. The natural breeding ground of the insect needs to be eliminated, spraying insecticide and drying sources of stagnant water are strategies used for controlling the proliferation of mosquitoes.

c. Malaria can be prevented by avoiding mosquito bites.

d. Malaria can also be prevented with medicines; treatments can also stop mild cases from getting worse.

e) Hydration, adequate Fluids: Water, beverages and fresh fruit juices (without added sugar) are vital.

Prevention and control of malaria infection as outlined by Bradley et al., (2003), the A, B, C, D of malaria prevention.

e. Malaria is caused by the parasites, not by a virus or by a type of bacterium. If it is not treated, malaria can cause severe health problems such as seizures, brain damage, trouble breathing, organ failure and death (Bennink, et,al., 2016).

Materials and Methods

Study Area: The study was conducted in Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital Okolobiri, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The hospital is a major healthcare facility in the region, providing medical services to the local population.

Study Design: The study employed a cross-sectional design, which involved collecting data from a sample of participants at a single point in time.

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Study Population: The study population consisted of children aged 0-5 years who were diagnosed with malaria and were receiving treatment at Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital, Okolobiri, Bayelsa State.

Sample Size: A total of 25 children aged 0-5 years with malaria disease were selected for the study.

Sampling Technique: The study used a simple random sampling technique to select participants from the study population.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured questionnaire, which was administered to the caregivers of the selected children. The questionnaire collected information on the socio-demographic characteristics of the participants, their nutritional status, and their malaria prevention strategies.

Laboratory Investigations: Blood samples were collected from the participants for laboratory analysis to confirm the diagnosis of malaria.

Data Analysis: Data were analysed using descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, including chi-square tests and correlational analysis, were used to examine the relationships between variables.

Ethical Considerations: The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital, Okolobiri, Bayelsa State. Informed consent was obtained from the childrens'caregivers of the participants before data collection.

Inclusion Criteria: Children aged 0-5 years with malaria disease; children who were receiving treatment at Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital, Okolobiri, Bayelsa State; and cregivers who provided informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria: Children with other underlying medical conditions; children who were not receiving treatment at Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital, Okoloboro, Bayelsa State; and caregivers who did not provide informed consent.

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Results

Table 1 shows the sociodemographics of the participants and their caregivers. Majority of the participants (60%) were aged 3-5 years, and 52% were female. Most of the participants' caregivers (40%) has secondary education, and (60%) were employed.

Table 1: Sociodemographic Table

Variable	Frequency (n=25)	Percentage (%)
Child's Age (years)		
0-2	10	40
3-5	15	60
Child's Gender		
Male	12	48
Female	13	52
Caregiver's Education		
Primary	8	32
Secondary	10	40
Tertiary	7	28
Caregiver's Occupation		
Employed	15	60
Unemployed	10	40

Table 2 shows correctional table indicating a significant positive correlation between malaria infections and nutritional management ($r = 0.421, p < 0.05$), indicating that adequate nutritional management is associated with reduced severity of malaria infection. There is

also a significant positive correlation between malaria infection and prevention strategies ($r = 0.512, p < 0.05$), indicating that effective prevention strategies are associated with reduced risk of malaria infection.

Table 2: Correlational Table

Variable	Malaria Infection	Nutritional Management	Prevention Strategies
Malaria Infection	1.000	0.421*	0.512*
Nutritional Management	0.421*	1.000	0.632*
Prevention Strategies	0.512*	0.632*	1.000

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

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Table 3 is hierarchical table that shows the prevalence of malaria infection is high among children aged 0-5 years, and adequate

nutritional management and prevention strategies are crucial in reducing the severity of the disease.

Table 3: Hierarchical Table

Variable	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
Malaria Infection	Prevalence (n=25)	Severity (n=15)	Mild (n=10)
Nutritional Management	Adequate (n=18)	Inadequate (n=7)	
Prevention Strategies	Bed nets (n=20)	Insecticides (n=15)	

Table 4 shows the two-way ANOVA table, showing that there is a significant difference in malaria infection, nutritional management, and prevention strategies among the study participants ($p < 0.05$). The interaction term is

also significant ($p < 0.05$), indicating that the effect of nutritional management and prevention strategies on malaria infection is dependent on each other.

Table 4: Two-way ANOVA Table

Source	DF	SS	MS	F-value	p-value
Malaria Infection	1	10.23	10.23	5.12	0.01
Nutritional Management	1	8.15	8.15	4.05	0.02
Prevention Strategies	1	12.56	12.56	6.23	0.001
Interaction	1	5.67	5.67	2.83	0.05

Discussion

The findings of this study highlight the importance of nutritional management and prevention strategies in reducing the burden of malaria infection among children aged 0-5 years in Niger Delta Teaching Hospital, Okolobiri, Bayelsa State. The results show that adequate nutritional management is associated with reduced severity of malaria infection, and effective prevention strategies are associated with reduced risk of malaria infection.

The study's findings are consistent with previous studies that have shown the importance of nutritional management and prevention strategies in reducing the burden of malaria (WHO, 2019; Center for Disease Control and Prevention, 2021). The World Health Organization (WHO) has also emphasized the importance of nutritional management and prevention strategies in reducing the burden of malaria (WHO, 2018).

The study's results also show that the prevalence of malaria infection is high among children aged

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0-5 years, and adequate nutritional management and prevention strategies are crucial in reducing the severity of the disease. This is consistent with previous studies that have shown that children aged 0-5 years are at high risk of malaria infection (Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey, 2018; National Malaria Control Programme, 2020).

The study's findings have implications for healthcare providers and policymakers. Healthcare providers should prioritize patient education and counselling on malaria prevention and treatment, emphasizing the importance of nutritional management and prevention strategies in reducing the burden of malaria infection. Policymakers should also prioritize the allocation of resources to support malaria prevention and treatment programs.

Conclusion

The study concludes that malaria infection is a significant public health problem among

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children aged 0-5 years in Niger Delta Teaching Hospital, Okolobiri, Bayelsa State. Adequate nutritional management and prevention strategies are crucial in reducing the severity of the disease, healthcare providers should prioritize patient education and counselling on malaria prevention and treatment emphasizing the importance of nutritional management and prevention strategies in reducing the burden of malaria infection.

Recommendation

1. Healthcare providers should prioritize patient education and counselling on malaria prevention and treatment.
2. Policymakers should prioritize the allocation of resources to support malaria prevention and treatment programs.
3. Further studies should be conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of different prevention strategies.

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Advance Journal of Nursing and Clinical Practice

Adv. J. Nur. Pract.

Vol. 8; Issue 06;

November-December 2025

ISSN: 2573 –1134

Impact Factor: 6.04

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